

stadium I, 3.0 ± 0.7 d; stadium II, 3.3 ± 0.4 d; stadium III, 2.6 ± 0.8 d; and stadium IV, 3.3 ± 0.5 d. Survival was 88%.

On *E. crus-galli* ssp. *hispidula*,

development took 20.1 ± 1.6 d with a similar incubation period; stadium I, 3.3 ± 0.6 d; stadium II, 3.3 ± 0.5 d; stadium III, 2.6 ± 0.4 d; and stadium IV, $3.3 \pm$

0.5 d. Survival was 84%. Adult longevity in both host plants was 5.6 ± 1.6 d. All the host plants tested, including rice (TN1), served as ovipositional hosts. □

Water management

Evapotranspiration and deep percolation loss of water in summer rice on lateritic soil

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We studied evapotranspiration and deep percolation in irrigated rice culture during summer 1987-88.

Permanently installed lysimeters ($3 \times 3 \times 1.5$ m) were filled with layers of lateritic soil (37% sand, 17.3% silt, and 45.7% clay having bulk density 1.45 g/cm³ and infiltration rate of 4.42 cm/h). Two lysimeters with closed taps were used for continuous submergence and two with open taps for irrigation scheduled at 25 mm CPE (Cumulative Pan Evaporation).

Rice (Ratna) seedlings were planted in the field and in the lysimeters at the same densities. Fertilizer, weeding, and other cultural operations were similar.

Water use was measured daily from transplanting to harvest in the continuous submergence treatment and after each irrigation in the scheduled irrigation treatment. In the continuous submergence treatment, loss of water was measured as the decline in water level. Soil was submerged to 5 cm after each observation. Loss of water through percolation was measured by the water collected in the irrigation treatment lysimeters. Loss of water from the scheduled irrigation treatment represented evapotranspiration + deep percolation, that from the continuous submergence treatment represented evapotranspiration only.

Combined loss of water due to deep percolation + evapotranspiration

Water use in irrigated rice.^a Ratnagiri district, M. S., India.

Growth stage	Continuous submergence		Scheduled irrigation at 25 mm CPE				
	ET (mm)	ET/d (mm)	Water use (mm)	ET (mm)	ET/d (mm)	Percolation (mm)	Percolation/d (mm)
Transplanting to tillering	285.15 (40)	13.58	672.21 (41)	169.83 (27)	8.09	502.39 (50)	23.92
Maximum tillering to panicle initiation	232.78 (32)	8.03	366.66 (22)	170.78 (27)	5.89	195.89 (19)	6.75
Panicle initiation to harvesting	197.67 (28)	5.99	611.10 (37)	297.61 (47)	5.72	313.50 (31)	6.03
Total or av	715.17 (100)	8.62	1650.00 (100)	638.22 (39) ^b	6.26	1011.78 (61) ^b	9.92

^a Figures in parentheses represent the percentage of the corresponding total of the column. ^b Percent of total water use (row). ET = evapotranspiration. CPE = cumulative pan evaporation.

amounted to 1,650 mm, of which 1,012 mm (61%) was attributed to percolation and 638 mm (39%) to evapotranspiration (see table). Evapotranspiration under continuous submergence was 12% higher than under scheduled irrigation.

Evapotranspiration was highest from transplanting to maximum tillering, and decreased thereafter. Percolation/day was highest during early crop growth stages. □

Postharvest technology

Utilization of rice by-products

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Rice bran, a high volume by-product of rice milling, is a source of protein, oil, nutrients, and calories. Its use varies from fuel to food, including fertilizers, pharmaceuticals, soap, and animal feed. We evaluated the rice bran of short-, medium-, and long-duration varieties for their edible oil content.

Five grams raw rice bran were collected after brown rice was milled in a Kett laboratory model polisher. The bran was air-dried for 6 h and its oil

content extracted with refluxing boiling point 40-60°C petroleum ether in a Soxhlet extractor.

Saket 3 bran had the highest oil content, N22 the least (see table). The correlation between growth duration of the varieties and oil content of the bran was not significant. □

Bran oil content of some short-, medium-, and long-duration rice varieties, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Oil (%)
Saket 3	95	21.7
N22	100	15.5
Saket 4	105	18.3
T3	125	19.6
IR24	125	17.8
T9	150	18.8
T100	150	19.4
Jalmagna	200	19.0
LSD (0.05)		1.2
Correlation between duration and oil content = 0.02		